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**Evaluation of users' attention and
navigation in a 2D and 3D environment
game by using NIPGBoard visualization
tool**

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Human-computer interaction (HCI) is a research field that focuses on the design and usability of the joint platforms, analyzes user's behaviour while one is using computer or other devices, e.g. smartphones or tablets. To design software or interfaces that enable people to interact with computers in novel ways, it is important to analyse the behaviour and underlying patterns of potential users, to understand how they interact with the device and the reasons for the actions they take.

Over the years of the development, the aim of the human-computer interaction expanded and broadened to many different fields. HCI is used in education, medicine, commerce, it helps people to use computer with different input modalities, improves user interface and etc.

A trending approach is to use Virtual Reality (VR) based systems. They are highly popular in educational purposes, e.g. pilot training systems, simulation of clinical surgeries, in entertainment scope, where companies release new VR games and simulators, in architecture and construction areas, VR can be used to translate the drawings from a plan into a 3D representation and many others.

People's behaviour also needs to be analysed in this three-dimensional framework, but for several reasons, new methods need to be used compared to traditional observation and data collection techniques. First of all, while being in a VR world, a person use all his body for navigation, therefore, his head, hands and legs movements can be analyzed. Second, the field of view in virtual reality world, in comparison with the computer-based systems, is wider - a person can rotate his head or body to look around. Gaze analysis take place here and helps in understanding behavioural patterns of the user. Moreover, the input devices are different - people do not use mouse

and a keyboard, but it is more likely controllers, that one put in his hands, and the virtual reality headset, that connected to the computer via cable or remotely. Thus, due to the difference of the standard, daily used devices and VR equipment, this should also be taken into consideration while conducting the research. For computer and mouse-control the desk and the chair is needed, but for VR much more space is required to avoid bumping into the furniture and walls. One can use VR while sitting, however, in this case it is less interaction.

The goal of the project is to evaluate and compare users' navigation techniques and performances in two different environments - 2D and 3D - while playing a simple outlier searching game. The 2D and 3D refer to the number of dimensions during the navigation.

The task for the user is to use two different interfaces while playing a game where the goal is to find the defected images among the defect-free ones. The environments are: (1) 2D as a visualization tool that runs in web browser and (2) 3D environment created with special virtual reality device.

The 2D tool is the NIPGBoard (based and similar to [1]) interface, that has many functions to display and compare different deep neural network outputs, but in this research we only used its data visualization capability. One of its main area, the so called projection panel is used to visualize high-dimensional data as miniature images in the 2D or 3D projection space after dimension reduction method application.

In 3D a special application was developed with Unity 3D. A virtual reality (VR) device, namely, HTC VIVE Pro Eye¹, was connected to the Unity² program, user actions can be carried out with the VR controllers. This device is one of the few VR devices that is capable of eye tracking that could reveal extra details about the participants' inner states.

The research and development steps were the following:

1. Literature overview regarding virtual reality and different user navigation techniques and evaluations of the collected dataset
2. Getting familiar with NIPGBoard software and related development components
3. Setting hypotheses
4. Development of the games in both environments and their testing

¹HTC VIVE Pro Eye device: <https://www.vive.com/eu/product/vive-pro-eye/overview/>

²Unity Pro Product: <https://store.unity.com/products/unity-pro>

5. Preparation of the protocols, conducting pilot experiments
6. Conducting real experiments
7. Evaluation and results

The structure of this paper is the following: first, the brief introduction of relevant papers, that overview similar problems like: mouse and gaze analysis, comparison of virtual reality and 2D navigation, studies regarding attention evaluation. Second, in the Background section the detailed description of the research question and challenges, the description of the used tools for development and evaluation and the related methodologies are placed. Next, in the Methods section more detailed explanation of the algorithms and list of smaller, pre-defined research tasks can be read. The following Experiments chapter describes how experimental research was conducted with the participants, especially, which protocol was followed. Data collection details are also listed here. The Evaluation chapter describes the previously obtained plots and figures for regression and classification tasks and also the processed logs. Results section is for visual and numerical results of the conducted research. As the final chapter I summarize and conclude the work.

Chapter 2

Related works

Nowadays it is a technological trend to involve more natural computer or interface operation/control methods, while using a notebook, personal computer or other devices. Some of the common examples are voice control, hand gestures or eye movements. These new technologies set new tasks for developers such as voice or hand recognition, designing devices for gaze tracking etc. There are already implemented solutions in the market but still a lot has to be done to facilitate natural human-computer interaction.

As we use computers and different systems in our daily life, researches tend to analyze cognitive factors, inner states, engagement level and many other important parameters of the users. Eye movements and human gaze in general provide us information about the target of attention, human's hidden intention, interests and other cognitive or emotional parameters as well. This is useful knowledge especially in human-computer interaction scenarios. However, link between gaze and mouse and their trajectories can be debatable question. Urška Demšar and Arzu Çöltekin [2] introduced in 2017 analytic methodology for mouse and gaze moves, collected real data for both movements and tested developed method on it. As a result, authors tentatively suggested that mouse tracking can potentially provide similar information as eye-tracking and used as a proxy attention.

A lot of research explored whether it is useful to use gaze movements instead of mouse movements. Efficiency of the gaze as an input modality had been compared to mouse input modality [3]. The space exploration game had been developed in Unity with both mouse-based and gaze-based modalities. Two players played the

same game, one of them was using the mouse, the other one was using the gaze. Interestingly, the participants took 1.7 second on average to perform the selection task using mouse, but the same participants took 3.43 seconds on average to conduct the same task using gaze. Preferred method of input, based on the questionnaires, was mouse.

Different search, navigation and visualization tasks had been solved with VR in the past. Adam Drogemuller, Andrew Cunningham et al. presented [4] a comparison between different navigation VR techniques such as teleportation, one-hands flying, two-hands flying and world in miniature. An important part of the paper is that one-hands flying and two-hands flying had been found as the fastest and easiest navigation techniques to perform.

Some papers explored gaze-driven navigation in virtual environment. Chris Christou, Kyriakos Herakleous et al. compared [5] compares gaze-directed and pointing method when one chooses a translation point in solving a maze game. Interestingly, gaze-directed method produced slightly better performance in terms of speed and accuracy. Users' gaze movement data while solving the way finding task was analyzed and the model that decides whether one needs any navigation aid was introduced [6]. The gaze-driven interface was used for a simple shooting game in [7].

Bernhard E. Riecke, Bobby Bodenheimer et al. analyzed [8] navigation techniques in VR. Participants had been asked to do navigational search task with two types of navigation. In one case, people were translating and rotating with the joysticks, in other case, with doing physical moves. As a result, physical walking showed performance benefits over using joysticks for navigation purposes. Controlling translation with the joysticks and rotation with the physical moves yielded to comparable performance as in real walking.

Regis Kopper et al. designed and evaluated [9] navigation techniques in multiscale environment were observed. This is the environment, where one can travel inside the object and see more details. Authors developed two techniques for multiscale navigation, namely, target-based and steering-based. As a result, target-based performed better in terms of navigation than the steering-based.

Analyzing users' behaviour while solving a maze game appeared to be quite popular problem among the researchers. One of the possible tasks is to ask users to navigate in a maze with a head-mounted display, search for the items and collect them [10], [11]. Although these papers gave an overview about possible types of navigation and tasks in VR, few of them compared the results with the same task in 2D space by using desktop environment and mouse and a keyboard.

Sonia E. Cárdenas-Delgado et al. presented [12] comparison of VR and 2D navigation. The result was that users performed better while using the desktop environment for solving the maze game, than with a virtual ones. Participants found more objects, the average speed was higher, however, the amount of collisions was roughly the same.

Different studies regarding attention evaluation in VR had been made. For example, paper-based and VR-based cancellation tasks to train sustained and selective attention [13]. Importantly, participants were satisfied more with VR conditions, than with a paper-based. Gang Li, Joaquin A. Anguera et al. conducted [14] two experiments to compare attention task performance on two different platforms - traditional computer monitor and HMD VR. It revealed, that selective attention is enhanced when using HMD-VR platform. The effectiveness of working memory training in the classroom can be assessed [15]. Authors aimed to measure attention process of the participants from elementary school. They were asked to view a series of letters on the blackboard while being in VR classroom and heat spacebar only after observing "X" preceded by an "A". They found out that cognitive abilities employed in the virtual classroom represent a much broader transfer of learning than traditional neuropsychological measures.

Chapter 3

Background

This chapter contains subsections in the following structure: first, additional details about the outlier searching game and the dataset we used are described. The next subsection is about the web browser-based environment and the relevant dimension reduction techniques. The third subsection is the technical description of the VR environment. At the end additional materials are mentioned.

3.1 Outlier Searching Game

Game Concept Outlier searching game is the game where one has to find N outliers among normal images. In our case, the outliers are images that show objects or surfaces that are damaged in some way: most of them are contaminated or show the consequences of some harmful impact. The aim of the game is to find all N outliers as fast as possible. A person cannot unclick or unselect already selected images, therefore, the number of errors should also tend to be zero. The time interval of the game is restricted to some T as well. During the gameplay, there are no additional restrictions on the user's actions, everyone can choose his own strategy freely and change it from one stage to another.

Game Design and Implementation The game was implemented for two different environments - for 2D and for 3D. In 2D, the NIPGBoard web-page interface was modified, the following plugins had been added: *timer*, *outlier* and *selected*. Moreover, to add some features, some parts of the code were modified in other plugins. *Timer* plugin implements time on the right panel, that counts from time T downwards zero. When time is up, a person see a pop-up message that the outlier

searching game has finished. *Outlier* plugin counts the number of selected outliers. This number is displayed on the right panel, a user can always check how many outliers are found and how many outliers are left. *Selected* plugin makes it possible to show image in better resolution once a participant click on it. Moreover, on the right panel are located helpful messages like 'Outlier found!', 'Not an outlier!', 'This outlier was already selected!' and F1 score.

To make the environment more interactive, apart from mentioned plugins, when a person clicks on the image, then it highlights with red if the image was not an outlier and green if it was an outlier. The whole image group is highlighted with green if all outliers per group had been found. This idea was implemented for both environments. Moreover, when participant gazing an image in the VR space, than it has some bluish overlay on top of it. In 2D - image has this overlay as well, however, it is connected to the mouse hovering actions.

In 3D, the game was developed with Unity3D and C#. Everything was developed from scratch. The difference between 2D and 3D case is the input modalities. While using the 2D, a person can navigate with a mouse and a keyboard, while in 3D a user is wearing the VR headset and use controllers. We tried to make the design of the game as identical as possible for both environments.

Participants were asked to participate in the outlier searching game. The aim of the game is to find 10 outliers, 2 outliers for each group. There were two time parameters - either 10 or 15 minutes. Overall, each participant had to perform 6 game stages:

1. NIPGBoard with 10 minutes
2. NIPGBoard with 15 minutes
3. VR one-handed flying 10 minutes
4. VR one-handed flying 15 minutes
5. VR two-handed flying 10 minutes
6. VR two-handed flying 15 minutes

The order of the stages had been assigned randomly for each participant. To ensure the same parameters during the experiment, the game's difficulty level, number of tasks and the environment will be the same or as similar as possible.

During both types of navigation, the needed logging had been performed, so that the obtained data can be analyzed after the experiments.

Image representation To represent images in 2D or 3D space, image embeddings had been used. Users were observing the data as clustered cloud of images in the 3D representation space, where they can navigate with different kind of methods according to the environment limitations. So participants can "go closer" to one class and observe it from different points and then switch to another one.

To generate clustered images, fully connected intermediate layer of the pre-trained VGG16 [16] for 2D case and ResNet50 [17] for 3D case was used. Predictions were run on this layer and the embeddings had been obtained. Both networks were pre-trained on ImageNet dataset.

Dataset Both game environments used the MVTeC Anomaly Detection dataset [18], which consists of 5000 high-resolution images. It includes 15 classes, each category comprises a set of defect and defect-free images. The image is labeled as a defect if an object on this image has some scratches, contamination, broken parts or cracks. The image is called defect-free when a normal, clear and unharmed object/surface is visible.

In the experiment we used 5 classes, namely, *bottle*, *hazelnut*, *leather*, *tile* and *transistor*. Each image set contained 50 images with no defects and 2 with defects. Some examples of the selected anomalous images are displayed in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: From left to right: bottle, hazelnut, leather, tile and transistor samples from the MVTeC Anomaly Detection dataset. For each of them, one defect-free image (top row) and one image that contain anomalies (bottom row) are displayed.

In this project users' performance in two different environments are compared, namely, 2D or NIPGBoard and 3D or Virtual Reality (VR).

3.2 Web Browser-based Environment

Embedding TensorFlow projector Embedding projector [1] is a web application available on a TensorFlow platform. Embedding is a map from input data to points in Euclidean space. It is useful approach to interpret machine learning models.

In general, embeddings exist in high-dimensional space, so it is useful to project the data into lower dimensional space to make it understandable to human observers. Tensorboard projector offers four dimensionality reduction techniques: Principal Components Analysis (PCA) [19], Uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) [20], t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) [21] and custom one.

One can explore the dataset both in 2D and 3D views and navigate by zooming in and out, shifting, change size of the points, focus on nearest neighbours points. The example of the projector with the images from MNIST database [22] is represented on Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Example of Tensorboard projector tool with MNIST image dataset

NIPGBoard The 2D tool is the NIPGBoard software developed by the Neural Information Processing Group (NIPG) of the Faculty of Informatics of Eötvös Loránd University in collaboration with the start-up Argus Cognitive. It is based and similar to [1] that is used to visualize high-dimensional data in the 3D projection space.

NIPGBoard has many extra functions and extensions comparing to the TensorBoard interface. It is capable to display outcomes of different pre-trained

deep neural networks, supports data exploration and includes human expert knowledge to the further training process via additional algorithms. It is a proper platform for domain experts to analyse their data without comprehensive knowledge about artificial intelligence. However, in this research we are only focusing on its data visualization function.

While navigating in NIPGBoard, a mouse and a keyboard can be used. A user can zoom in, zoom out and rotate the 3D projection space. Additionally, user can check better image resolution on the hovering panel on the right while hovering mouse cursor on the image. After clicking on the image, the image will be constantly on the selection panel, until the next click happens. The example of the NIPGBoard environment with clicked and hovered image is represented on Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Example of NIPGBoard tool visualization with MVTeC Anomaly image dataset, when leather image was selected and hovered

Common Dimensionality Reduction Techniques Dimensionality reduction techniques are useful methods to transform datapoints from high-dimensional space into a lower dimensional space. Sparse data is usually used in machine learning tasks, therefore, these methods are used to overcome the curse of dimensionality and to make computations possible to analyze.

One of the most popular method is Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [19]. PCA is geometric parameter-free approach: it looks for axis that explains as much variance of the data as possible. It is widely used in exploratory data analysis and for making predictive models. It is a linear method, that has different variations, such as Kernel PCA, Sparse PCA and others.

Another technique is called t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) [21]. In comparison with PCA, t-SNE has many parameters that should be taken into consideration, such as perplexity, early exaggeration and parameters related to the gradient descent part of the algorithm. It is a nonlinear statistical method, highly useful for visualization purposes.

Uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) [20] is nonlinear technique, that is similar to t-SNE, but it assumes that the data is uniformly distributed on some manifold.

On Figure 3.4, PCA, t-SNE and UMAP algorithms had been applied to the iris flower dataset [23].

Figure 3.4: Three dimensionality reduction techniques: PCA, t-SNE and UMAP - applied on iris flower dataset

3.3 Virtual Reality (VR) Environment

Virtual Reality is a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world. VR was rapidly developing over the past decades. Many companies developed and released their VR headsets for education, entertainment and other purposes, e.g. Oculus Rift (2010), Google Cardboard (2014), HTC VIVE SteamVR (2016), Labo (2019). VR is an alternative user interface which offers great benefits in many areas, gives opportunity to interact in the immerse world as in the same one¹.

According to [24], there are seven concepts that describe virtual reality: simulation, interaction, artificiality, immersion, telepresence, full-body immersion and network communication. Three features, also called three 'I', are important from a technical point of view, namely, immersion, interaction and imagination.

¹Dom Barnard, 'History of VR - Timeline of Events and Tech Development', Virtual Speech, last modified 6 August 2019, <https://virtualspeech.com/blog/history-of-vr>

There are several challenges that one can face while dealing with VR environment. First of all, most of the Virtual Reality Head-mounted display (HMD) devices are connected via cable to the computer. Therefore, it leads to the limits in interaction and freedom of movement. It is also important to mention that the room, where one experience VR headset, should be free from furniture, as there is always a chance to bump into it while moving around with the headset. Another problem is that VR environment, due to the human's eyes constant refocus, can cause sickness, tiredness and fatigue. Moreover, even though new devices can look fashionable and modern, they still can be heavy on your head or look clumsy. All of these should be taken into consideration while conducting the research with VR. There are already developed standard questionnaires that you can use, e.g. simulator sickness questionnaire [25], sense of presence questionnaire [26].

Virtual Reality Implementation In 3D environment, a special application had been developed with Unity 3D. A virtual reality (VR) device, namely, HTC VIVE Pro Eye, was connected to the Unity program, user actions can be carried out with the VR controllers. SteamVR plugin and Tobii packages had been used as well to ensure connection between Unity and the headset. This device is one of the few VR devices that is capable of eye tracking that could reveal extra details about the participants' inner states. While doing the literature review, it was found that preferable navigation techniques in 3D environment are either one-handed flying (navigating with one controller) or two-handed flying (navigating with two controllers). Both navigation techniques will be used during the experiment.

Unity engine Unity is a cross-platform game engine developed by Unity technologies and released in 2005. It is widely used to develop computer games. There are several advantages of using Unity:

1. Understandable editor which simplifies the process of game development
2. Great for rendering both 2D and 3D scenes
3. Detailed documentation
4. Ability to connect with Virtual Reality headset
5. Asset store gives opportunity to download packages (e.g. Tobii and SteamVR packages had been used)

However, there are several disadvantages as well:

1. Even though prefabs are quite useful and easy to use, editing these templates can be quite complicated
2. Sometimes it can be hard to find scripts, that are linked to the objects
3. Unity does not support links to external code libraries

Unity supports JavaScript and C# for scripting. The reason to choose Unity in combination with C# was because of my previous experience with the language and high availability of support for C# and Unity.

3.4 Additional Materials

There are several materials that had been used apart from 2D and 3D environment. One of them is the *attention test*. Attention test was based on dot-cancellation or Bourdon test [27]. The idea of using this test is to check users' attention and compare his performance with the performance in the game.

Before completing the game, participants had to know the dataset. Therefore, the *sample learning game* was performed with Python GUI. Users had to recognize outlier by comparing two given images.

To have some correlations between the user and his personality, Big Five Inventory-2 (shortly BFI-2) [28] form was filled. This form offers new opportunities for research examining the structure, assessment, development, and life outcomes of personality traits.

3.5 Models Used for Evaluation

There are several estimators that had been used for evaluation purposes. Let us describe them in some details.

Support Vector Machine Support Vector Machine or SVM is one of the machine learning algorithms used for classification and regression analysis problems. It is designed in such a way that it looks for points on the graph that are closest to the boundary hyperplane. These points are called support vectors. Then, the algorithm calculates the distance between the support vectors and the separating hyperplane.

This distance is called the margin. The main goal of the algorithm is to maximize the margin distance. The best hyperplane is the hyperplane for which this margin is as large as possible.

Random Forest Classifier Random Forest Classifier [29] is a tree-based supervised learning algorithm. In our project it was used for feature extraction purposes. It is a tree-based algorithm, therefore, features of X that are chosen at the top of the tree are usually more important than features that are selected at the end nodes of the trees.

Support Vector Regression Support Vector Regression [30] works on the principle of the Support Vector Machine, but is used for regression tasks. In SVR the curve is not used as a decision boundary, but it is used to find the match between the vector and position of the curve. It supports both linear and non-linear kernels.

K-means algorithm K-means is an iterative algorithm that tries to partition the dataset into K clusters or subgroups, where each data point belongs to only one group. K-means follows Expectation-Maximization algorithm [31], where E-step is assigning the data points to the closest cluster and M-step is computing the centroid of each cluster.

Chapter 4

Methods

This chapter provides more detailed explanation about those scientific methods and applied algorithms that have closer relation with the actual series of experiments. We will go through the data preprocessing steps, then on those technical details that are connected with the data collection phase. Many logging scripts were developed for this purpose, which is one of my main contributions to the research. As it was mentioned before, eye-tracking has many potentials towards analysis of human behavior. This chapter also describes separately the two kind of eye-tracking applications in the 2D and 3D environments. As additional data collection, the attention test and Big Five Inventory-2 form will be introduced from the proposed evaluation's point of view. The last two bigger subsections (4.9 and 4.10) are about the focused explanations of the main evaluation directions that are towards solving a regression and a classification task.

4.1 Data Preprocessing

Special techniques had been used to visualize images in a clustered cloud of points. Similar preprocessing steps were used for two game environments. Different pre-trained deep neural networks were providing the images' hidden representations (embeddings), and we had some changes in the dimension reduction phase as well. Detailed explanation can be read in the following paragraphs, separately for the 2D and 3D cases.

For the 2D case: Images of the dataset were preprocessed to the size of (224, 224, 3), where (224, 224) is the image size and 3 means that it is an RGB image. After

that VGG16 model from Keras, that was pre-trained on ImageNet dataset [32], was used. Top layers were included. However, we do not need to have the output of the model, we just want to have the embedding vector. Therefore, we use the fully connected intermediate layer and run our prediction on it. Before running NIPGBoard on server, the *embedding* folder should be created, it has model checkpoint, sprite image (sample sprite image can be seen on Figure 4.1) and metadata file, that has information about the image filename and its id. We should also have *images* folder, that contains the image dataset and configuration **.json* file, that gives path to the embedding and dataset folder during the configuration process. After that, we can run NIPGBoard on a server. The data visualization and application of PCA (among other choosable dimension reduction techniques) are automatic functions of the interface.

Figure 4.1: Example of the set of sprite images for NIPGBoard projector

For the 3D case: Images of the dataset were preprocessed to the size of (224, 224, 3). After that ResNet-50 model from Keras, that was pre-trained on ImageNet dataset, was used. Top layers were included. Similarly to 2D case, we run prediction on average pooling layer. We applied PCA with 50 components, and after that, to get x , y , z coordinates for our game, we apply t-SNE algorithm, so that the clustering is present. There are several reasons to use t-SNE before PCA. One of them is that

t-SNE is computationally expensive and one can face the curse of dimensionality problem. Therefore, dimensions were reduced with PCA first.

4.2 Experimental Tools

4.2.1 Virtual Reality

The virtual navigation task ran on an AMD Ryzen 7 2700 Eight-core computer, 3.2 GHz processor with 32 GB RAM, an NVIDIA GeForce GTX-1080 video card, and Windows 10 Home Operating System. For the development of the virtual environment, we used Unity Edition Professional, version 2020.3.1f1, as the game engine.

The HTC VIVE Pro Eye device (Figure 4.2) was used during the experiments in Virtual Reality. It contains VR headset, two bases and two controllers. This device also has an HDMI connector that needs to be plugged into the HDMI port of the graphics card of the computer. This device has a resolution 1440×1600 per eye, a field-of-view of 110 nominal, an optical frame rate of 90 Hz.

Figure 4.2: HTC VIVE Pro Eye VR device: headset in the middle, bases are in the upper corners and controllers are in the lower corners [33].

To integrate HTC VIVE Pro Eye with navigation task the SteamVR plugin was used. The Unity MainCamera has to be replaced by the camera of the Player prefab. The scripts required for the integration were programmed with C#.

Two types of navigation had been developed, namely, *one-handed flying* and *two-handed flying*. In one-handed flying mode, a user has to pull either right (if he/she is right-handed) or left (if he/she is left-handed) trigger to fly and move his hand in the direction he wants to fly. Using a controller in VR activities is similar to easy

physical exercise, so we recommended the participants to use their dominant arm. To stop the flying mode, the trigger has to be pulled again. Two-handed flying mode works in a similar fashion, however, both triggers have to be pulled.

Flying techniques In this brief section we will use the general geometrical agenda for vectors and positions in the three-dimensional coordinate system to describe one-handed and two-handed flying techniques. The definitions of positions cover the usual, geometrical x, y, z coordinates, and the vectors are either have own sign or defined as the combination of the starting and ending positions' capital letter.

Let us define hand position (either left or right hand) as H and head position as K . The direction vector will be calculated as a $\vec{D} = H - K$. If current position of the user is U , then new position after flying will be $U + \vec{D}$.

For two-handed flying, we calculate separately left and right direction: $\vec{L}\vec{D} = LH - K$, $\vec{R}\vec{D} = RH - K$, where $\vec{L}\vec{D}$ - left hand direction vector, LH - left hand position (x, y, z coordinates), $\vec{R}\vec{D}$ - right hand direction vector and RH - right hand position (x, y, z coordinates). The final direction vector will be calculated as $\vec{D} = \vec{L}\vec{D} + \vec{R}\vec{D}$. If current position of the user is U , then new position after flying will be $U + \vec{D}$. This description is visualized on Figure 4.3 and its corresponding subfigures.

Figure 4.3: Visual illustration of the calculated vectors and given positions for the two kind of flying techniques. The blue rectangles represent the controllers, the headset is not depicted on the wooden manikin.

While navigation in VR space, the user can see the gaze representation as a small white bubble. Images are highlighted with a light blue overlay if the user is looking on them. To select an image, a participant has to push the controller's touchpad while looking at the image. Image will be immediately highlighted with either green (if it is an outlier) or red (if it is a defect-free image) color. Overall, 10 outliers have to be found (2 outliers per class). When both of the outliers (images with defect) are found in the actual image class, then all the related images in this class become highlighted with green. Thus, from this point, the whole image category has green overlay, it can be excluded from the outlier searching task which makes it easier for the participant to solve the task. It helps the user to focus on the remaining images, that he has probably not observed yet. Figure 4.4 illustrates "inner view" of the real VR experiment, when a person found two outliers from the transistor class, thus, all members of the transistor class became green.

Figure 4.4: Screenshot from the real VR experiment, when both outliers in transistor class were found.

4.2.2 NIPGBoard

The 2D navigation task ran on an Intel Xeon E5-2620 version 4 personal computer with 64 GB RAM and 2.10 GHz, and with an NVIDIA GeForce GTX-1080 video card.

NIPGBoard is an online, interactive visualization tool, which was built based on the Tensorboard embedding projector. The projector is a web application, that represents the data in a 3-dimensional space. The backend of the application is written with Python, for the frontend - Typescript programming language is used. Additional plugins had been added to the original NIPGBoard version, namely, *outlier*, *timer* and some of the scripts had been modified to make the environment more interactive. Timer plugin implements the 10 or 15 minutes timer visualization for the participant. Outlier plugin calculates the F1 score and displays the text to the participant like 'Outlier found!', 'Not an outlier!' and 'This outlier was already selected!'. The modified scripts are located in projector plugin, the color for the hovering and selected outliers and non-outliers had been added. During the navigation, all mouse movements and clicks are sent as a POST requests to the server and saved into a **.txt* file.

To implement gaze tracking, Tobii Pro Nano eye-tracker was used. It is a screen-based eye tracker which captures gaze data at 60 Hz and is designed for fixation-based studies. The device is located on the bottom of the screen. Before each experiment in 2D environment, it was calibrated with Tobii Desktop Application. During the calibration process, user's head position is adjusted, after this he has to follow

nine dots, located in different parts of the screen, to calibrate the gaze. Example photos of the calibration process from the real experiment can be seen on Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Tobii Pro Nano calibration process: on the left - calibration of the head position, on the right - calibration of the gaze.

To record necessary logs, the sample python script that use *tobii_research* library had been implemented. The gaze logging script is run before each NIPGBoard experimental stage and stores the x , y coordinates of the participant's gaze to the file and the corresponding timestamps.

4.3 Logging

Our motivation was to log every user action that is possible to receive the most detailed data for later reproduction of the experiment, that is the key of proper evaluation. The following information with the timestamps had been saved in NIPGBoard interaction tool during the experiment:

1. Mouse clicks (X, Y) coordinates and mouse movements (X, Y) coordinates
2. Camera moves (it is logged when user rotates the cloud of points) (X, Y, Z) coordinates
3. Hovered and selected image names
4. Screenshots of the screen in **.jpg* format
5. Gaze 2D (X, Y) coordinates from Tobii Pro Nano device
6. High-definition face video from a simple webcam with HD recording capability

For Virtual Reality the logs are similar, but related to 3D space. Each log, similar to 2D case, contains the timestamp as well:

1. Controller clicks

2. Image names hovered by gaze
3. Turning on and off the flying mode
4. Position of the user in 3D space (comes from Unity in (X, Y, Z) format)
5. Gaze origin (comes from HTC VIVE in (X, Y, Z) format)
6. Normalized gaze direction (comes from HTC VIVE in (X, Y, Z) format)
7. Screenshots of the screen in **.jpg* format

4.4 Gaze Tracking in VR

4.4.1 Coordinate Systems

To process logs from Unity environment and Tobii device, Python programming language was used. The following logs are crucial to be visualized and used in the evaluation process:

1. Position of the user in 3D space
2. Gaze origin
3. Normalized gaze direction

The information about user's position in 3D space comes from Unity, while the gaze origin and gaze direction (X, Y, Z) coordinates are obtained from *Tobii* API. To visualize them using Python *Plotly* library, we have to convert (X, Y, Z) coordinates to the same coordinate system space. Unity and Tobii has different coordinate system from the Plotly. To get the right representation, X coordinate remained in X position, Y coordinate became Z , Z became Y . Therefore, we transferred coordinates from right-handed coordinate system to the left-handed coordinate system as it is visually explained in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: Coordinate systems: (a) left-handed coordinate system, used in Unity; (b) right-handed coordinate system, used in Python Plotly and Tobii API

4.4.2 Gaze Ray and Image Intersection Algorithm

To analyze which images had been observed at which timestamp, we had to apply ray-plane intersection algorithm.

The image can be represented as a center point p with 4 corner points p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 (Figure 4.7). Based on the preset parameters in Unity, by knowing the center coordinate p , we can get the corner points by using equations 4.1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_1 &= (p_x, p_y - L, p_z + L) \\
 p_2 &= (p_x, p_y + L, p_z + L) \\
 p_3 &= (p_x, p_y + L, p_z - L) \\
 p_4 &= (p_x, p_y - L, p_z - L)
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

where L - half length of the image, which was equal to 4.

Figure 4.7: Image corner coordinates in 3D space.

As we know gaze origin and gaze direction coordinates, we can use images as planes and apply ray-plane intersection algorithm, where ray will be the gaze ray. We will use gaze origin and normalized direction vector. The whole process with the relevant explanation and the list of equations from 4.2 to 4.7 will be described below.

The algorithm is the following:

1. Find plane normal

$$N = (p_2 - p_1) \times (p_3 - p_2) \quad (4.2)$$

2. Make it a unit vector:

$$N = \frac{N}{\sqrt{(N_x^2 + N_y^2 + N_z^2)}} \quad (4.3)$$

3. Define gaze ray with the origin point g_o and direction vector g_d
4. Calculate the following scalar product:

$$D = \langle N, g_d \rangle \quad (4.4)$$

5. If D not equal to zero, then calculate the parameter t

$$t = -\frac{\langle N, (g_o - p) \rangle}{D} \quad (4.5)$$

6. If t is more than zero, construct gaze ray by using the following equation:

$$Q = g_o + t \times g_d \quad (4.6)$$

Thus, Q is the intersection point.

7. Now we need to check that the found point lies inside the image plane.

Therefore, the following equations have to be checked:

$$\begin{aligned}c_b &= p_2 - p_1 \\e_b &= p_4 - p_1 \\ \langle p_1, c_b \rangle &\leq \langle Q, c_b \rangle \leq \langle p_2, c_b \rangle \\ \langle p_1, e_b \rangle &\leq \langle Q, e_b \rangle \leq \langle p_4, e_b \rangle\end{aligned}\tag{4.7}$$

4.5 Gaze Tracking in NIPGBoard

Analyzing gaze coordinates with NIPGBoard is a more difficult task. The reason for this is that the web panel can be rotated, zoomed and shifted, so it is difficult or impossible to tell from the (X, Y) screen coordinates which image was observed, as the computer screen and the projector image may be different on the same timestamps.

Since it is not possible to clearly define the target of the gaze, we assumed to divide the screen into the main and important areas that have different purposes. The decision was made to divide the panel to 4 sections - *projector*, *hovered*, *selected* and *other*. Projector is the place of observation and navigation, selected and hovered panels are for checking and comparing particular images in better resolution, and other area is for additional information gathering and minor user actions. Figure 4.8 shows the predefined areas of the web page (that is mainly the NIPGBoard interface) with the corresponding color codes. When the user is observing images in the projector panel, so the gaze coordinates are inside the defined area, then it can be said that the selected section will be *projector*. Similarly, for the *hovered* and *selected* panels. Any other area outside the aforementioned three main sections are belong to the *other* panel area. As we know the (X, Y) coordinates of the panels and (X, Y) gaze screen coordinates, it is not hard to say where the position of the gaze was.

Figure 4.8: The division of NIPGBoard web page to four main panels for gaze analysis.

4.6 Learning Game

Learning game is a simple, short game, developed with Python GUI, namely, the *tkinter* library. Two images are visualized at the same time, next to each other, from the same image class. The user’s task is to choose the outlier from the two displayed samples. For each class two pairs of image comparisons had been done. Images for the learning game had been chosen randomly, but remained the same for all participants. Participants were allowed and encouraged to ask questions about correct and incorrect answers. This stage was not part of the actual experimental data collection phase, the aim was just to make it easier for participants to recognise outliers, so we wanted to ensure that all participants understood and familiarised themselves with all the image categories and their associated example errors.

4.7 Attention Test

We had a preconception that human attention may play a role in the user performance score in the outlier searching game. We decided to explore whether there is any relation between the participants’ level of attention and other metrics measured during the game, e.g. the number of outliers found or the number of wrong selections. To do this, before the experiment starts, a simple attention test is made. The test that was chosen is called dot-cancellation test or Bourdon test. The test was carried out for each participant as a pen and paper test. The appearance of the

test is quite simple: on the given page a participant can see groups of black dots, that are located one by one on several lines. The task is to cross the groups of four points among the groups of three and five points. It is important to go line by line, do not jump from one part of the paper to another. After one minute the conductor stops the participant, collects the paper and gives a new one to repeat the task with the new groups. This procedure repeats five times.

The following parameters are taken into consideration for the evaluation for the paper M :

1. Number of wrongly selected points
2. Number of missing points (skipped/not selected)
3. Number of correctly selected points
4. Total number of errors
5. Viewed percentage of the paper

After that, the following metrics were calculated:

1. Total number of points groups viewed N
2. Total number of wrongly selected points A_{n_0}
3. Total number of correctly selected points N_0
4. Total number of mistakes made A_0
5. Total number of skipped groups A_p

The accuracy (processing precision) and the speed are the parameters, that can access adult's attention level. The speed V is calculated as a total number of points viewed divided by total time (Equation 4.8), and accuracy K is calculated as a difference of total number of points viewed and number of mistakes made, divided by the total number of groups viewed (Equation 4.9).

$$V = \frac{N}{t} \tag{4.8}$$

$$K = \frac{N - A_0}{N} \tag{4.9}$$

4.8 Big Five Inventory-2 Form

The Big Five Inventory or BFI-2 form includes 60 questions about personality. One can choose one of the following answer for the offered questions: disagree a little, neutral (no opinion), agree a little, agree strongly.

Based on the person's answers, the following personal traits can be analyzed:

1. Sociability
2. Assertiveness
3. Energy level
4. Compassion
5. Respectfulness
6. Trust
7. Organisation
8. Productiveness
9. Responsibility
10. Anxiety
11. Depression
12. Emotional volatility
13. Aesthetic sensitivity
14. Intellectual curiosity
15. Creative Imagination

These traits compose five main personal characteristics, namely, extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, negative emotionality, open-mindedness.

4.9 Regression Tasks

In regression problems, the set of answers y has the form of R or R^m . Tasks of this type are usually associated with forecasting. For example, by given certain car parameters, e.g. fuel efficiency, engine capacity, top speed and others, predict the car price.

In this project, two regression tasks had been set:

1. By having BFI-2 form personality traits, predict the number of misclicks
2. By having BFI-2 form personality traits, predict the number of found objects

Let's overview both cases in more details.

4.9.1 Input Data for Regression Tasks

In both tasks, X data for the model is the same - BFI-2 form features, but the target y is different. For the first task, y is the total number of misclicks, for the

second task, y is the total number of found objects. The BFI-2 form consists of 20 personality traits. Those are values from 0 to 100. We have this data for all 30 participants. To create X for training and for testing, these values were standardized using *StandardScaler* package in *scikit* Python library. It standardize features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance. Standardizing is needed, in other case variances will not be comparable. After this, 20 features were compressed into two components with PCA. For both cases these compressed components had been used as X data.

As each participant has $n = 6$ different stages, to calculate the number of misclicks M and construct target y , all the misclicks were summed up (Equation 4.10):

$$M = \sum_{n=1}^6 m_n \quad (4.10)$$

where m_n is the number of misclicks for the corresponding stage.

Similarly, the number of found objects F was calculated (Equation 4.11):

$$F = \sum_{n=1}^6 f_n \quad (4.11)$$

where f_n - number of found objects at stage n .

As the number of instances is limited to 30, in one iteration the model will be trained on 29 samples and being tested on 1. The selection of the test data will be shifted, and the remaining samples will cover training data. After this process, we receive 30 test results.

4.9.2 Model Applied for Regression Task

To solve the regression task, Epsilon-Support Vector Regression (SVR) estimator is used from *scikit* Python library with the linear kernel.

4.10 Classification Tasks

Classification task in machine learning is a problem, where we have a finite number of class labels y , and for each object the model should calculate the corresponding class label. For example, by having different parameters, that describe a

bank client, e.g. gender, age, profession, education, family income, loan amount and others, decide whether to give him a credit or not. In this case, y are elements from a set $\{-1, 1\}$. where -1 - issue a loan on this application, 1 - reject this application. If the number of classes equals two, then we call it *binary classification problem*. If the number of classes are more than two, then we call it *multiclass classification problem*. In our evaluation we addressed both classification tasks.

In our particular case the class labels will refer to participants' performances, which was first defined as two or three different classes. The starting point of the classification was the BFI-2 form traits for the first case, and the attention test results for the second case.

According to the aforementioned setup the following classification tasks had been set:

1. By having BFI-2 form personality traits, predict class label - best, medium or worst performance
2. By having BFI-2 form personality traits, predict class label - best or worst performance
3. By having processing speed and accuracy from the Attention test, predict class label - best, medium or worst performance
4. By having processing speed and accuracy from the Attention test, predict class label - best or worst performance

Before solving the classification tasks, we have to define classes for our unlabeled data. The class labels are referring to the participants' performance groups based on game logs.

4.10.1 Defining Performance Groups with K-means

We used K-means to see how it can decompose the data into the clusters. In the first case we use the game logs as input data. To do this, for each participant we calculate the sum of found objects, sum of misclicks and sum of time spent over all 6 game stages. Thus, for each participant we have 3 values, that can describe his performance: total found outliers, total misclicks, total time spent. After that, PCA was used and 2 principal components had been obtained. We repeated this process two times, first one without standardization and second time with standardized data.

4.10.2 Input Data for Classification Tasks

The X data for this experiment is the same as in the regression task - compressed to 2 components BFI-2 form. The target y is the class label, that was obtained from k-means algorithm.

4.10.3 Feature Selection

While solving the task and having limited amount of data (as we had just 30 participants), it can be useful to do feature selection. That means that from 20 BFI-2 personality traits we will use just N features. To do that, Random Forest classifier was applied, where X was all BFI-2 form features, while y was the class label.

4.10.4 Model Applied for Classification Tasks

To solve the classification task, Support Vector Machine is used from *scikit* Python library. For the first task, where we have 3 classes, the Radial-basis function (RBF) kernel is used. For the second task with 2 classes - linear kernel is applied. Due to the imbalance in the dataset, the class weight parameter in the SVM was set to *balanced*. This mode uses the values of y to automatically adjust weights inversely proportional to class frequencies in the input data.

Chapter 5

Experiments

Previous papers published in the topic of navigation in 2D and 3D space have been measuring the effectiveness separately, only few papers compared both environments. For more details, please visit the Related Works chapter and the papers mentioned within.

Although these papers give an overview of the possible navigation techniques and users' preferences, the comparison of two environments is an important milestone. To achieve this we use MVTec Anomaly Detection dataset and techniques described in Chapter 4.

5.1 Pilot Experiments

Two pilot experiments were conducted before the real experiments had been started. One of the volunteers in the pilot experiment was a naive user in video gaming, other involved person was an experienced user.

Originally, we were supposed to use 10 image classes, however, in this case the time for each experiment will be significantly increased or it will be not possible for the them to solve the task during the 10 or 15 minutes time constraints. We also experienced when the volunteers become too tired, it is hard to properly focus and finish the games. One important conclusion made was to set a reasonable limit on the maximum time that a game stage can last. After different setups, we concluded to have 10 and 15 minutes game plays and training games before the real ones.

We also practiced how to clearly explain the game environment, VR flying techniques, so that it is understandable for the participants. We encouraged volunteers

to ask questions and alert us if something was not clear in the preparation or explanation. Main conclusions of the pilot experiments were that we defined (to ourselves) the proper order of the preparation tasks, finalized the content of the overall explanation (written form) and defined the approximate time per stage.

The whole experimental data collection become around 3 hours, where the preparation and explanation took approx. 1,5 hour, actual experiments' maximum time is 75 minutes (3 times 10 minutes plus 3 times 15 minutes), and we calculated extra time for rest between the game stages and any other unexpected technical issue.

5.2 Game Dataset

For our experiment we used the MVTEC Anomaly Detection dataset, which consists of 5000 high resolutional images.

Originally, 10 classes had been used. However, after the pilot experiments, we decided to reduce the number of classes to 5 due to the time constraints for each participant for fulfilling the task. Moreover, a subjective analysis about all the classes had been made, where the most difficult classes had been excluded from the experiment, e.g. toothbrush, pill, cable.

For each game stage unique dataset had been used. Before experiments started, 8 datasets were generated. Six of them were the main ones, and last two are the backup versions for extreme cases, e.g. a person felt dizzy while VR navigation, computer ran out of memory, logs could not be saved or if any other technical issue occurs. Each dataset contains 50 defect-free objects and 2 defect objects per category, they were chosen randomly, no repetition for outliers happened in all 8 datasets. So, altogether 250 defect-free images and 10 outliers per dataset and every class has 52 images.

5.3 Participants

University students and NIPG members participated in the experiment ($N = 30$). All of them completed the task and filled the questionnaires. The mean age is 26.267, there were 11 women and 19 men. 29 participants were right-handed, 0 were left-handed, 1 was ambidextrous. 15 participants did not need to correct their vision, 2 wear contact lenses, 13 were wearing glasses. The mean number for overall

gaming skill is 6 (in a scale from 1 to 10, where 10 - very good, 1 - very poor). The participants were tested individually. Each experiment took approximately 3 hours.

To keep initial conditions for all participants, they were asked not to discuss the experiment with each other. The GDPR form was explained and signed by each of them before the experimental phase began.

5.4 Protocol

The experiment has 3 phases: first, overall explanation and introduction, then a training phase and finally the actual experiment. The flowchart of all the steps is represented on Figure 5.1.

The experiment starts with an instruction period, where main parts of the game are explained to the participant. Next, the GDPR, BFI-2 and general information forms are filled.

The participants are asked to complete a simple attention test, which is described in Chapter 4. Moreover, to eliminate doubts of the participants about whether the image is an outlier or not, a simple learning game was developed. The participants are asked to compare two images and decide which one has an object with defect. All in all, two pairs per class were presented. Lastly, to complete the training phase, before navigating in virtual environment, participants tested both navigation techniques - one-handed flying and two-handed flying. The training data was used, that contains carpet, grid, wood and pill classes of the same MVTec Anomaly dataset. These classes are not used in a real experiment, however, the amount of outliers and non-outliers remained the same, as in a real experiment. Neither in learning game, not in virtual reality training, the data or participant's performance was not recorded.

Figure 5.1: Experiment flowchart

The experiment consisted of 6 main stages. The order of the stages were assigned randomly to each participant after the instruction period. The possible stages are:

1. Navigation in Virtual Reality within 10 minutes period with One-Handed flying technique
2. Navigation in Virtual Reality within 15 minutes period with One-Handed flying technique
3. Navigation in Virtual Reality within 10 minutes period with Two-Handed flying technique
4. Navigation in Virtual Reality within 15 minutes period with Two-Handed flying technique
5. Navigation in NIPGBoard within 10 minutes time period
6. Navigation in NIPGBoard within 15 minutes time period

The amount of outliers were the same for each participant and for each experimental stage, however, to exclude the fact that users have memorized the images with outliers, the defect images were different for each stage.

After each experimental stage users have to fill the simulator sickness form and a questionnaire, that asks them to rate the type of navigation that they performed. The solutions for the game, that was just finished, are shown upon request to eliminate further doubts.

During the navigation in NIPGBoard and in VR, users are constantly getting feedback from the system. While hovering the image, it highlights with a light-blue color. If a user click on it and this image is an outlier, than it will be highlighted as green until the game finishes. If the chosen image was not an outlier, than it will remain red. When all the defect images of one class were chosen, then the whole cloud of points is highlighted with green color, what helps users to focus on the rest of the classes. Moreover, the user can see the timer, F1 score and the number of outliers selected. This information was constantly displayed and updated in a well-visible location.

Each participant has one attempt to complete the experimental stage. However, if one feels dizziness or fatigue during the navigation in virtual reality, then the experiment stops and the user can repeat it later, but the dataset of the game will be changed. Users get rest upon request.

Lastly, participants have to fill the sense of presence and overall user experience forms.

Chapter 6

Results

There are many parameters that can be taken into consideration, while analyzing the performance or behaviour of the participants. In this section figures, tables and plots illustrate different numerical outcomes. We go through game performance analysis, where we describe how participants were divided into two and three different groups based on their performance in the game stages. Next, attention test parameters and visualization of the participants' results takes place. Then, trained model results for the regression and classification tasks are illustrated. Lastly, gaze analysis plots in both 2D and 3D environments are shown.

Participants ID 0 and 1 were used during the pilot experiment, thus, all the data for the 30 participants is from participant 2 to participant 31. Figures in this chapter will include information only about p2-p31.

6.1 Game Performance

The parameters, that we can use from the logs of the game are the following:

1. Number of found objects (discrete number, maximum possible number is 10 per game stage, in total 60)
2. Number of not found objects (discrete number, minimum number is 0)
3. Number of misclicks (discrete number)
4. F1 score (discrete value between 0 and 1)
5. Time spent per stage (in seconds)
6. Time spent per image group (in seconds)

6.1.1 Performance Groups without F1 Score

We used K-means to see how it can decompose the data into the clusters. The related performance data were: total found outliers, total misclicks, total time spent. PCA was used and 2 principal components had been obtained. In Figure 6.1 the visualization of K-means algorithm with 3 clusters can be seen. Annotation values, e.g. p2, p3 and etc., are the participants ID.

Figure 6.1: K-means clustering for the participants' performance with $k=3$.

After that calculations, participants are divided into 3 groups as *best* (7 instances), *worst* (7 instances) and *medium* performance (16 instances). On Figure 6.1, purple group refers to the worst performing, green cluster - medium performing and yellow cluster - best performing group.

On Table 6.1 the minimum, maximum and mean values for total number of found objects, total number of misclicks and total time spent are represented for 3 clusters.

After standardization of the data, we repeated the aforementioned processing steps. In this case we obtained 2 clusters. We titled these groups as *best* (20 instances) and *worst* (10 instances) performing classes. The visualisation can be seen on Figure 6.2. Yellow cluster refer to the best performing group, purple cluster refer to the worst performing group.

TASK 1	worst			medium			best		
	MIN	MAX	MEAN	MIN	MAX	MEAN	MIN	MAX	MEAN
Number of found objects	40	56	49	48	60	54.44	48	60	56.14
Number of misclicks	6	54	21.43	4	28	12.19	3	15	8
Time spent (in sec)	3813	4358	4049.29	3139	3691	3454.06	1957	2932	2554.29

Table 6.1: Minimum, maximum and mean values for the participants performance in the games for each cluster (multilabel classification)

Figure 6.2: K-means clustering for the participants' performance with $k=2$

On Table 6.2 the minimum, maximum and mean value for total number of found objects, total number of misclicks and total time spent are represented for 2 clusters.

6.1.2 Performance Based on F1 Score

By calculating F1 score (Equation 6.1) for all the stages, we can analyze participants' performance. Number of found objects will be used as true positive (TP) values, number of misclicks as false positive (FP) values and number of not found items as false negative (FN) values.

$$F1 = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN} \quad (6.1)$$

TASK 2	worst			best		
	MIN	MAX	MEAN	MIN	MAX	MEAN
Number of found objects	40	57	49.7	48	60	55.5
Number of misclicks	6	54	20.9	3	18	9.6
Time spent (in sec)	3393	4358	3899.5	1957	3691	3124.75

Table 6.2: Minimum, maximum and mean values for the participants performance in the games for each cluster (binary classification)

As each participant had 6 stages, let us sum up all the values, that we use in the calculation, and find F1 score. In Figure 6.3 the sorted F1 score is represented for each participant.

Figure 6.3: Sorted F1 score for all the game stages

The parameter that was not used in F1 score is the time spent per stage. Let us sum the values of time for all 6 stages and sort them. The maximum value that can be achieved is 75 minutes (4500 seconds), as there are 3 stages with 15 minutes (900 seconds) time mode and 3 stages with 10 minutes (600 seconds) time mode. The sorted values are illustrated on Figure 6.4

Figure 6.4: Time spent for all game stages

6.2 Attention Test

The main parameters, that should be taken into consideration, are the processing speed and accuracy. The mean speed value for all the participants is 187.27, mean accuracy is 0.97. The speed was calculated as a total number of points viewed divided by total time (Equation 4.8), and accuracy was calculated as a difference of total number of points viewed and number of mistakes made, divided by the total number of groups viewed ((Equation 4.9)). The attention test's result as the processing speed on the X axis and accuracy displayed in the Y axis is represented in Figure 6.5.

Figure 6.5: Attention test results

Attention test values were also used in the classification task. Attention test parameters - standardized processing speed and accuracy - had been used as X , and y label was utilized from the game performance clustering, that we described before. Therefore, the class label y can be either best, medium and worst or best and worst performances. On Figure 6.6 you can see attention test results, where X axis is a processing speed, y axis is a accuracy and the color of the datapoints is the color, taken from the k-means game performance clustering and assigned to each participant p2-p31.

Figure 6.6: Coloring attention test results with the class labels from kmeans

We can also calculate F1 score (Equation 6.1) for each participant, by using total number of correctly selected groups as a true positive (TP) value, total number of wrongly selected groups as a false positive (FP) value and total number of skipped groups as a false negative (FN) value. The mean value for F1 score is 0.92. On Figure 6.7 sorted F1 score is visualized for all participants.

Figure 6.7: Sorted F1 score for attention test

6.3 Regression Task

The tasks were described in Methods section. Let us overview the results of the trained models.

For both tasks we will calculate the relative error by using the following equation:

$$\frac{|y_{true} - y_{pred}|}{y_{pred}} \quad (6.2)$$

where y_{true} is the actual, real number from our data and y_{pred} is the predicted value by the model.

Relative error tells us the error in relation to the actual value, it puts the size of the error into perspective.

6.3.1 Task 1: Predict number of misclicks

In the Figure 6.8 the real and predicted number of misclicks were visualized over the training stage. In the Figure 6.9 relative error is visualized. Index of the

experiment refers to the model training phase.

Figure 6.8: Predicted and real values for number of misclicks

Figure 6.9: Relative error values for number of misclicks

6.3.2 Task 2: Predict number of found objects

In the Figure 6.10 the real and predicted number of found objects were visualized over the training stage. Next, relative error is visualized on Figure 6.11. The maximum number of found objects is 60, as the number of correctly selected objects per game is 10.

Figure 6.10: Predicted and real values for number of found objects

Figure 6.11: Relative error values for number of found objects

6.4 Classification Task

As it was described in the Methods section, there are two classification tasks to be solved - with 3 class labels (best, medium, worst performance) and with 2 class labels (best, worst performance). For each task, there are several options for X data. The variants are the following:

1. X - all BFI-2 form features
2. X - BFI-2 form features, importance of which is more than 0.08
3. X - top three BFI-2 form features
4. X - features from BFI-2 form, selected manually

For each task the confusion matrix was constructed. By having confusion matrix, precision, recall and other parameters can be calculated.

First of all, let us show the results (Figure 6.12) of the Random Forest Classifier, where the feature importance can be seen for classification task 1 and task 2.

(a) For multilabel problem (task 1)

(b) For binary problem (task 2)

Figure 6.12: Sorted feature importance from Random Forest Classifier

6.4.1 Task 1: Solving multilabel classification problem for BFI-2 form

In Table 6.3 the SVM model performance with RBF kernel is represented. In task 1 we have 3 class labels, for each class precision, recall and F1 score was calculated by using micro-averaging approach. Micro averaging follows the one-vs-rest approach. It calculates precision and recall separately for each class with True - if class label predicted as actual one, and False - if class predicted is not an actual class, irrespective of which wrong class it has been predicted.

TASK 1	worst			medium			best		
	precision	recall	F1 score	precision	recall	F1 score	precision	recall	F1 score
All BFI-2 form features	0.25	0.43	0.32	0.45	0.31	0.37	0.14	0.14	0.14
Top 3 BFI-2 form features	0.62	0.71	0.67	0.5	0.25	0.33	0.21	0.43	0.28
BFI-2 form features, importance of which is more than 0.08	0.36	0.57	0.44	0.55	0.38	0.44	0.5	0.57	0.53
Manually selected features from BFI-2 form	0	0	0	0.16	0.06	0.09	0	0.14	0.11

Table 6.3: Model performance values for task 1

6.4.2 Task 2: Solving binary classification problem for BFI-2 form

In Table 6.4 the SVM model performance with linear kernel is represented. In task 2 we have 2 class labels, for each class precision, recall and F1 score was calculated. The same micro-averaging approach to calculate the metrics was applied.

TASK 2	worst			best		
	precision	recall	F1 score	precision	recall	F1 score
All BFI-2 form features	0.19	0.4	0.26	0.33	0.15	0.21
Top 3 BFI-2 form features	0.5	0.6	0.56	0.78	0.7	0.74
BFI-2 form features, importance of which is more than 0.08	0.38	0.6	0.46	0.71	0.5	0.59
Manually selected features from BFI-2 form	0.13	0.3	0.18	0	0	0

Table 6.4: Model performance values for task 2

6.4.3 Task 3 and 4: Solving classification problem for attention test results

By having attention test results and y as a class label the following confusion matrices were obtained (Figure 6.13):

(a) For multilabel problem (task 1). Cluster 0 - worst performance, Cluster 1 - medium performance, Cluster 2 - best performance

(b) For binary problem (task 2). Cluster 0 - worst performance, Cluster 1 - best performance

Figure 6.13: Confusion matrices for the model, that predicts class label for Attention test results

6.5 Gaze analysis

Even though the results in gaze analysis have not been achieved yet, I would like to visualize some plots that have already been done.

The 3D visualization plot had been done for the VR environment. It contains the flying path (Figure 6.14) of the person, images from the real experiment, that were represented as a 4 corner points and 1 center point, and also the gazing points (Figure 6.15) on those images. The detailed explanation, how gaze points, which are intersections between the gaze ray and images, were found - you can find in section 4.4.

Figure 6.14: Visualization of the user flying path in VR environment

Figure 6.15: Visualization of the user gazing points in VR environment

For 2D environment, the plots, that contain the following information, were generated: clicked images and correctness of the click (the outline of the circle is red if the non-outlier was selected and green if the defect image was selected), camera

move actions (zooming in and zooming out, shifting), mouse hovering actions, gazing in different projector panels over the the whole game stage(Figure 6.16).

Figure 6.16: Visualization of the user gaze on different projector panel, mouse clicks, hovers and camera move in NIPGBoard environment

Chapter 7

Discussion

In this research, we wanted to understand whether there is any connection between user's performance in the game or attention test and his/her personality traits from the BFI-2 form. Based on the trained models and achieved metrics, that we mentioned in the Results chapter, let us discuss what results had been achieved.

First of all, by doing clustering on the game performance data, it was clearly seen that people can be divided to either 2 or 3 groups. Based on the performance data, that we have for each participant, we found out that, those people who were fast in the game, they also had better performance, than those, who were slower (Table 6.1, Table 6.2).

If we discuss the regression tasks, by looking at the plots with actual and predicted values (Figure 6.8, Figure 6.10), it is seen that the model predicts nothing more but the average performance, BFI-2 form parameters does not affect the output. This is true both for the predicting number of misclicks and predicting number of found objects tasks. This outcome can be the result of having limited amount of data due to the limited number of people, who participated in the experiment.

By observing the tables, that shows the performance of the models in classification tasks, we can say that the best result was achieved by having top three BFI-2 form features, that were selected after Random Forest Classifier for each classification task (Table 6.3, Table 6.4). However, the result is insufficient for saying that the model can predict the class label from the BFI-2 form - both for binary and multi-class classification problem. This can be due to the imbalance in the dataset and small amount of data. Even though some methods were used to solve the first problem, the second one cannot be managed, as limited number of people participated

in the experiment.

The result, that was obtained for the attention test is quite interesting. By just looking at the plot (Figure 6.6) we can see that the division of the clusters, when we have 2 class labels, looks clear, well-divided, even though the colour of the points was based on the game performance clustering, not on the performance in the attention test. Going further with the task, when we used 2 class labels, the result obtained in the confusion matrix (Figure 6.13) is quite promising: precision equals 0.89, recall equals 0.8. Thus, even though two classes were imbalanced, the result, that was achieved, is quite good. It means that people who are defined as 'best' performing in the game, can be also defined as 'best' performing in the attention test. Similarly, for the 'worst' performing group.

All in all, we can conclude that there is a connection between performance in the game stages and performance in the attention test. However, it seems to be no connection between BFI-2 form personality traits and performance in the game. By having traits of the person, we cannot predict his/her performance during the game stages.

Talking about navigation in two environments, we did data exploration and we assume that better performance can be related with more efficient navigation. We prepared the components for navigation analysis, such as 2D plots about the users' actions (Figure 6.16) and 3D flying trajectory with the gaze points (Figure 6.14 and Figure 6.15). We would like to further analyze the time spent for each group observation, that we get from the gaze, and compare it with the performance in the game and in the attention test. By discussing with the participants their strategy during the game play, they usually told us the same or similar patterns - most of them were zooming out, observing one image group randomly or line by line, and when they finish with this group, they switch to another image cluster. It seems for us to be a good start for data analysis and further exploration.

Chapter 8

Conclusion and Future Work

In the thesis we have explored publications in a human-computer interaction topic, especially the one that are connected with the topic of our research - connection between mouse and a gaze movements, different flying techniques and gaze-driven navigation in Virtual Reality, analysis of user behaviour while solving a maze game, that is similar to our outlier searching game and etc. We developed a unique outlier searching game in two different environments - computer based (2D) and virtual reality (3D) based ones. After conducting pilot experiments, the setup of the protocol was made - we defined the order of the experimental stages, understood how to explain the dataset and the game logic to the participants and defined game time limits. Further, by conducting experiments with the participants, we obtained all the necessary information that was analyzed: mouse and gaze movements, screenshots of the screen, selection actions and etc. All of these lead to the following results: BFI-2 form features have no effect on the performance in the game, while the attention test performance and performance during the game stages have connection. Many programming tasks had been solved during the project: game development for 2D and in 3D environments with different programming languages, scripts for saving the logs, development of the Learning Game, various methods and algorithms for processing the logs and their visualizations.

In the future prospects, we want to analyze gaze patterns of the participants, check whether there is a relation between gazing patterns and BFI-2 form personality traits. It would be interesting to also compare the questionnaires about both environments and understand which environment and navigation technique was preferable for the users. We are also planning to have a publication about the

research, because a lot of possible connections have not been investigated yet, e.g. personal preferences for navigation techniques and their connection with the BFI-2 form, observation time per image and attention and others.

Chapter 9

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